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Scoil na nDomhaneolaíochtaí UCD

CAGEO
CENTRE FOR
APPLIED GEOPHYSICS
AND
DATA INTEGRATION

Methodology for measuring Chargeability, Compressional Velocity (V_p), Density, Galvanic Electric Resistivity, Gamma Ray Spectrometry (K, Th, U), Inductive Electric Conductivity, Magnetic Susceptibility, Portable X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF), and Shear Velocity (V_s) of drill core rock samples at the UCD Petrophysics Laboratory

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1. Introduction

This report describes the methodologies employed in the University College Dublin (UCD) Petrophysics Laboratory. The physical properties measured are 1) chargeability (also referred as induced polarisation - IP) with galvanic electric resistivity, 2) compressional velocity (V_p), 3) density, 4) gamma-ray spectrometry (K, Th, U), 5) inductive electric conductivity, 6) magnetic susceptibility, and 7) shear wave velocity (V_s). The chemical composition of the samples is estimated using a handheld portable X-ray fluorescence (pXRF) analyzer. The core samples for the measurements can have a diameter of 3.65 cm (BQ), 4.76 cm (NQ), or 6.35 cm (HQ) with approximately 10 cm in length and either full or split in half lengthwise.

2. Measurements for quality control

Before taking physical property measurements on the rock samples, a quality control measurement is taken on standard samples, with fixed reference values defined by their manufacturer, to ensure that the equipment internal calibration is correct and the measurements are coherent with the standard samples. Then, a quality control measurement is taken again on the standard samples once every ten rock samples are measured to ensure no equipment drifting or failure is happening. Table 1 shows the nominal values of the standards (Figure 1) for each of the physical properties measured.

Table 1 - Table of the fixed reference physical properties of the standards used in the UCD Petrophysics Laboratory.

Physical property	Standard BQ	Standard NQ
Chargeability (IP - induced polarization)	97.3 ± 1.0 mV/V	97.3 ± 1.0 mV/V
Compressional velocity (V_p)	2717 ± 25 m/s*	2717 ± 25 m/s*
Density	8 ± 0.16 g/cm ³	8 ± 0.16 g/cm ³
Galvanic electric resistance**	100.1 ± 1.5 k Ω	100.1 ± 1.5 k Ω
Gamma-ray spectrometry	18.2 ± 0.4 % K	18.9 ± 0.3 % K
	126 ± 3 ppm U	143 ± 1 ppm U
	129 ± 4 ppm Th	361 ± 2 ppm Th

Inductive electric conductivity	11.3 ± 2.9 S/m	13.5 ± 1.3 S/m
Magnetic susceptibility	$63.6 \pm 1.9 \times 10^{-3}$ SI	$97.3 \pm 2.9 \times 10^{-3}$ SI
Shear velocity (Vs)	256 ± 10 m/s*	256 ± 10 m/s*
Standard Reference Material NIST2711A for pXRF	100 ± 7 ppm As	100 ± 7 ppm As

* The values were defined empirically for the standards provided by the equipment manufacturer.

** Same standard as the one used for chargeability.

Figure 1 - Standards used in the UCD Petrophysics Laboratory for quality control measurements of a) chargeability (induced polarisation - IP) with galvanic electric resistivity, b) compressional velocity (V_p), c) density, d) gamma-ray spectrometry (K, Th, U), e) inductive electric conductivity, f) magnetic susceptibility, g) shear wave velocity (V_s), h) handheld portable X-ray fluorescence (pXRF).

3. Methodology for the physical property measurements

3.1. Density

The density of the samples is measured using an Ohaus Explorer EX1103 balance with an underhook weighing system (Figure 2). The samples are soaked in water for at least 24 hours before being measured. The measurement consists of two procedures: i) weighing the sample in the air by placing it over the balance top plate and ii) weighing the sample immersed in water with the assistance of a hook placed under the balance connected to a weighing basket. The density of the sample is calculated by the balance using the Archimedes Principle, where σ is the density of the sample, w_a is the weight of the sample in the air, w_l is the weight of the sample in the liquid, and ρ is the liquid's density (dependent on t).

$$\sigma = \frac{w_a \rho}{w_a - w_l} \quad (1)$$

The water's temperature (t) is measured using a thermometer every 10 measurements and updated in the balance. The water's temperature measurement accounts for any density changes in the water. The balance goes through auto-calibration every 3 hours.

Figure 2 – Density measurement system with the Ohaus Explorer Precision Balance showing the balance, for sample air weight, on top of a glass board with a hole to allow the connection of the under-balance hook cable to a basket that is immersed in water for underwater weight.

3.2. Magnetic Susceptibility and Inductive Electric Conductivity

The measurements are conducted using a KT20 console in scan mode equipped with a 10 kHz sensor for magnetic susceptibility and 100 kHz sensor for inductive electric conductivity, both curved sensors of appropriate dimensions (BQ, NQ or HQ) to fit the core sample (Figure 3). During the measurement, the sample is rotated 360 degrees at an approximately constant speed for 60 seconds. The values taken during this time interval are averaged and the maximum, minimum and standard standard deviation are computed to be included in the database.

Figure 3 - a) KT20 main console with curved sensor and b) conductivity and susceptibility sensors for the KT20 console.

3.3. Chargeability (IP) and galvanic electric resistivity

The chargeability (commonly referred as IP - induced polarization) and the galvanic electric resistivity of the samples are measured simultaneously using a KT20 console with the IP sensor connected to a sample holder (Figure 4). The IP/res mode requires that the metallic plates and electrodes of the sample holder are connected to the KT20 via electric cables to perform the measurement. The sample is placed longitudinally into the sample holder between two sponges, soaked in a saturated sodium chloride solution, to decrease the contact resistance between the samples and the plates. The measurements are made at 15 V for 5 stacks, with a 4-second measurement time.

Figure 4 - KT20 main console with chargeability/resistivity sensor and sample holder.

3.4. Compressional (V_p) and shear (V_s) velocity

The measurements are conducted using a Pundit Lab+ ultrasonic instrument (Figure 5) equipped with a pair of 150 kHz transducers for compressional velocity (V_p) and a pair of 40 kHz transducers for shear velocity (V_s). The sample is placed on a sample holder and the transducers at the plain edges of the sample (longitudinally). For V_p , the transducers are covered with coupling gel to allow the ultrasound waves to pass into the sample without reflecting off intervening air. For V_s , we use the Pundit Dry Point Contact (DPC) shear wave transducer with 5 pins with individual contact points, therefore coupling gel is not necessary. For V_p , the Pundit Lab+ is calibrated on a standard sample using a standard transit time of 25.4 μs and the default settings of transducer frequency mode on 150 kHz and pulse width at 9.3 μs . For V_s , the Pundit Lab+ is calibrated on a standard zeroing plate; the settings are adjusted to transducer frequency mode on 37 kHz and pulse width at 12.5 μs .

Figure 5 - a) Main console of the Pundit Lab (+) ultrasonic velocity meter connected to the V_p transducers and b) the V_s transducers.

3.5. Gamma-ray spectrometry

The natural gamma-ray radiation of the samples is measured using a Georadis GT-40 inserted in a shield that combines steel and lead materials to get maximum shielding efficiency and minimum weight (Figure 6). The measurement consists of placing the sample inside the equipment's desktop shielding and measuring the sample for 300 seconds, repeating the procedure three times per sample to improve the statistical significance. Quality control measurements are taken every 10 measurements on different standards for K, U, and Th of appropriate dimensions to match the diameter of the core samples. The quality control also includes the measurement of the background radioactivity (empty shield or a non-radioactive standard).

4. Geochemical measurements

4.1. X-ray fluorescence

The approximate bulk elemental composition of the samples is measured using an advanced handheld elemental analysis device, the portable Olympus Vanta M-Series X-ray fluorescence (XRF) analyzer (Figure 7a). The critical precision/absolute chemistry mode is used with two beams: the first for 5 seconds, and the second for 25 seconds. Each sample is measured at 6 discrete points (three on each side of the sample, Figure 7b), and the bulk composition is averaged. Quality control measurements are taken every 10 samples using two standards, one blank (glass) and a second one (standard material 2711A) with 100 ± 7 ppm arsenic. The procedure consists of scanning in the following order: blank, standard, standard, blank, before proceeding to further sampling.

Figure 7 - a) Olympus Vanta M-Series XRF analyzer in portable workstation mode and b) schematic illustration of a rock core sample with the distribution of the measurement points (red dots).

5. Raw data processing and database structure

Each piece of equipment used for the petrophysical and geochemical measurements have its specific configurations and formats for the raw data, which are automatically assigned fixed file names at download. In order to avoid replacement and/or duplication of raw files, we developed a database structure that does not require file renaming or editing after download. For this, the raw data is downloaded to a folder named by the date of data acquisition inside the folder associated with the specific physical property, both are created by the user. Then the following folders are created automatically by the specific equipment and stay as they are for data processing (Figure 8).

Figure 8 - Structure of the folders where the raw data is stored for each of the methods. DD-MM-YY refers to day (DD), month (MM) and year (YY).

The sample report is the file that connects the samples to their physical property measurements automatically for data processing. In the file, the user sequentially enters the measurement ID corresponding to each sample ID (unique ID assigned to each sample) and quality control measurement in the designated spreadsheet tab for each physical property measured. Additionally, any special circumstances (broken samples, samples that are above or below the equipment's detection limit, etc.) are noted.

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